

Structure-Stability-Activity Correlations in Ternary Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) Involving Heteroaromatic N-Bases as Primary Ligands and Some Pesticides as Secondary Ligands[†]

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The $\Delta \log K_M$ values in mixed ligand complexes of the type MAL^+ , where $M = Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II)$ or $Zn(II)$, $A = 2,2'$ -bipyridyl (bipy) or 1,10-phenanthroline (phen), and $L =$ phenoxyacetic acid (PAA), 2-chlorophenoxyacetic acid (2-CPA), 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D), 2,5-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,5-D), 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4,5-T), benazolin (ben) or salicylanilide (sal) have been calculated to explain intramolecular aromatic ring stacking in these complexes. The electronegativities (as stability ratio, SR) of ligand anions and MA^{2+} species and partial charges (q) on coordinating atoms (O and M) have been calculated theoretically which have supported stronger $d\pi \rightarrow p\pi$ bonding in $CuAL^+$ complexes than in other MAL^+ species. Also, linear relation between pK_a or stability constants ($ML^+ ML_2, MAL^+$ species with chlorophenoxyacetic acids) and Hammett σ -values has been observed which indicates structure-stability-activity correlations, thereby supporting their common mode of action.

It has been observed in our recent investigations^{1,2} that Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) form stable ternary complexes with 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy) or 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) as a primary ligand and indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), indole-3-propionic acid (IPA), indole-3-butyric acid (IBA) or naptalam as a secondary ligand which have supported complexation as a possible mode of action of these plant growth regulators or pesticides. Since binding of active molecules may produce changes in their conformation and reactivity^{3,4}, we felt that it would be of further interest to investigate specificity leading to selective and preferred interactions in some other compounds such as phenoxyacetic acid (PAA), 2-chlorophenoxyacetic acid (2-CPA), 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D), 2,5-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,5-D), 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4,5-T), benazolin (ben) and salicylanilide (sal). Thus, the stability of ternary M/N-base/pesticide [$M = Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II)$ or $Zn(II)$], complexes have been studied in solution to see if a particular ligand combination is favoured and if selectivity is achieved. The electronegativities (as stability ratio, SR) of ligand anions and MA^{2+} species and partial charges (q) on coordinating atoms (O and M) in these species have been calculated theoretically using Sanderson's approach⁵. These data have been used to interpret the tendency of back donation of electronic charge from the metal orbital ($d\pi$) to the available vacant orbital on the primary ligand ($p\pi$). The role of π -bonding, direct ligand-ligand interac-

tions and substituent effects in these ternary systems have been discussed and structure-stability-activity correlation has been explored.

Experimental

Metal nitrates used were of A.R. grade. 2,2'-Bipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline, PAA, 2-CPA, 2,4-D, 2,5-D, 2,4,5-T and salicylanilide were obtained from Fluka AG, Switzerland. Benazolin was obtained from Boots Co., London. Other chemicals were of B.D.H. AnalaR grade. Dioxane was used after purification. A 50-70% aqueous dioxane (v/v) was chosen as the medium to keep PAA, 2-CPA, 2,4-D, 2,5-D, 2,4,5-T, ben and sal and their complexes in solution.

The binary systems were investigated with 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio of the metal ion to the ligand (PAA, 2-CPA, 2,4-D, 2,5-D, 2,4,5-T, ben or sal) and the ternary systems with 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of the metal ion to the primary and secondary ligands as reported earlier^{1,2}.

Calculations :

The dissociation constants of bipy and phen and the corresponding stability constants of binary metal complexes have been taken from literature⁶. The protonation constants of PAA, 2,4-D, 2,5-D, 2,4,5-T, ben and sal and the corresponding stability constants of their binary (Table 1) and ternary (Table 2) metal complexes have been evaluated as reported earlier^{1,2}.

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TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS* OF BINARY METAL COMPLEXES OF PPA, 2-OPA, 2,5-D, 2,4-D, 2,4,5-T, BENAZOLIN AND SALICYLANILIDE

(T=25°; μ=0.1 M KNO₃)

Ligand	Metal ion	log K _{ML} ^M	log K _{ML} ^{ML}	log β _{ML} ^M
PAA (pK _a =4.46)	Co(II)	2.97	2.45	5.42
	Ni(II)	2.50	1.87	4.37
	Cu(II)	3.24	2.93	6.17
	Zn(II)	2.32	1.68	3.99
2-OPA (pK _a =4.43)	Co(II)	2.85	2.40	5.25
	Ni(II)	2.55	2.00	4.55
	Cu(II)	3.28	2.97	6.25
	Zn(II)	2.30	1.65	3.95
2,5-D (pK _a =4.39)	Co(II)	2.80	2.35	5.15
	Ni(II)	2.55	2.15	4.70
	Cu(II)	3.26	2.94	6.20
	Zn(II)	2.26	1.67	3.93
2,4-D (pK _a =4.27)	Co(II)	2.75	2.30	5.05
	Ni(II)	2.44	2.00	4.44
	Cu(II)	3.22	2.87	6.09
	Zn(II)	2.27	1.63	3.90
2,4,5-T (pK _a =4.15)	Co(II)	2.65	2.25	4.90
	Ni(II)	2.35	1.95	4.30
	Cu(II)	3.20	2.72	5.92
	Zn(II)	2.25	1.61	3.86
ben (pK _a =5.52)	Co(II)	3.37	2.75	6.12
	Ni(II)	3.27	2.89	6.16
	Cu(II)	3.58	2.97	6.55
	Zn(II)	3.27	2.85	6.12
sal (pK _a =9.68)	Co(II)	7.80	7.15	14.95
	Ni(II)	7.70	7.58	15.28
	Cu(II)	8.08	7.56	15.64
	Zn(II)	6.78	5.84	12.62

*Standard deviations :

pK_a, ±0.008-0.01 ; log K_{ML}^M, ±0.02-0.04 and

log β_{ML}^M, ±0.02-0.10.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS* OF TERNARY METAL COMPLEXES OF 2,2'-BIPYRIDYL AND 1,10-PHENANTHROLINE WITH PAA, 2-OPA, 2,5-D, 2,4-D, 2,4,5-T, BENAZOLINE AND SALICYLANILIDE TOGETHER WITH THE VALUES OF log K_M

(T=25°, μ=0.1 M KNO₃)

Primary ligand	Secondary ligand	Metal ion	log K _{MAL} ^{MA}	log β _{MAL} ^M	Δ log K _M
bipy	PAA	Co(II)	3.14	9.20	0.17
		Ni(II)	2.39	9.52	-0.11
		Cu(II)	3.55	11.55	0.31
		Zn(II)	2.50	7.80	0.18
bipy	2-OPA	Co(II)	3.07	9.13	0.22
		Ni(II)	2.47	9.60	-0.08
		Cu(II)	3.58	11.58	0.30
		Zn(II)	2.45	7.75	0.15
bipy	2,5-D	Co(II)	3.06	9.12	0.26
		Ni(II)	2.53	9.66	-0.02
		Cu(II)	3.53	11.53	0.27
		Zn(II)	2.42	7.72	0.16
bipy	2,4-D	Co(II)	3.19	9.25	0.44
		Ni(II)	2.40	9.53	-0.04
		Cu(II)	3.51	11.51	0.29
		Zn(II)	2.47	7.77	0.20
bipy	2,4,5-T	Co(II)	3.18	9.24	0.53
		Ni(II)	2.45	9.58	0.10
		Cu(II)	3.48	11.48	0.28
		Zn(II)	2.50	7.80	0.25
bipy	ben	Co(II)	3.58	9.64	0.21
		Ni(II)	3.46	10.59	0.19
		Cu(II)	3.82	11.82	0.24
		Zn(II)	3.25	8.55	-0.02

(Table 2 Contd.)

bipy	sal	Co(II)	6.28	12.34	-1.52
		Ni(II)	5.83	12.96	-1.87
		Cu(II)	7.69	15.69	-0.89
		Zn(II)	5.89	11.19	-0.89
phen	PAA	Co(II)	3.16	10.41	0.19
		Ni(II)	2.40	11.20	-0.10
		Cu(II)	3.67	12.92	0.43
		Zn(II)	2.55	9.10	0.23
phen	2-OPA	Co(II)	3.10	10.35	0.25
		Ni(II)	2.55	11.85	0.00
		Cu(II)	3.73	12.93	0.45
		Zn(II)	2.50	9.05	0.20
phen	2,5-D	Co(II)	3.10	10.85	0.30
		Ni(II)	2.65	11.45	0.10
		Cu(II)	3.66	12.91	0.40
		Zn(II)	2.51	9.06	0.25
phen	2,4-D	Co(II)	3.20	10.45	0.45
		Ni(II)	2.37	11.17	-0.07
		Cu(II)	3.65	12.90	0.43
		Zn(II)	2.53	9.08	0.26
phen	2,4,5-T	Co(II)	3.11	10.36	0.46
		Ni(II)	2.38	11.18	0.03
		Cu(II)	3.62	12.87	0.42
		Zn(II)	2.55	9.10	0.30
phen	ben	Co(II)	3.52	10.77	0.15
		Ni(II)	3.56	12.36	0.29
		Cu(II)	3.98	13.23	0.40
		Zn(II)	3.40	9.95	0.13
phen	sal	Co(II)	6.85	19.60	-1.49
		Ni(II)	5.93	14.73	-1.77
		Cu(II)	7.74	16.99	-0.34
		Zn(II)	6.04	12.59	-0.74

*Standard deviations :

log β_{MAL}^M, ±0.008-0.01, log K_{MAL}^{MA}, ±0.01-0.02.

Taking the mutual effect of both the ligands in a complex into consideration, the values of Δ log K_M, the characterizing factor, have been evaluated as follows :

$$\Delta \log K_M = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M = \log K_{MLA}^{ML} - \log K_{MA}^M \quad (1)$$

where,

$$\log K_{MLA}^{ML} = \log \beta_{MAL}^M - \log K_{ML}^M$$

These values have been reported in Table 2.

Using Sanderson's approach⁶, the electronegativities of secondary ligand anions and MA²⁺ species have been calculated from the atomic stability ratios of C, H, O, Cl, Ag and Ag⁺ and C, H, N, O, M(II), F and F⁻ respectively, thereafter partial charges on O and M(II) have been estimated. Some representative values have been listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONEGATIVITIES (SR) OF LIGAND ANIONS AND MA²⁺ SPECIES AND PARTIAL CHARGES (q) ON COORDINATING ATOMS (O AND M) IN THESE SPECIES

Ligand anion	SR	q on O atom	MA ²⁺ species	SR	q on M(II)
PAA	3.670	-0.324	Cu(bipy) ²⁺	4.056	0.501
2-OPA	3.741	-0.309	Cu(phen) ²⁺	4.033	0.494
2,5-D	3.811	-0.295	Zn(bipy) ²⁺	4.085	0.355
2,4-D	3.811	-0.295	Zn(phen) ²⁺	4.059	0.348
2,4,5-T	3.884	-0.279	—	—	—

Results and Discussion

Binary systems :

The titration curves (not shown) of binary complexes have almost similar nature for all the phenoxyacetic acids. The lowering of metal-ligand titration curve was more considerable for ben and even more for sal which indicated their high affinity towards a metal ion. The overall stability constants of binary complexes of phenoxyacetic acids do not follow Irving-William's sequence⁷ while those of ben and sal do so.

Ternary systems :

In 1 : 1 : 1 MAL systems, considerable lowering of pH from the corresponding binary mixtures indicated the formation of ternary complexes in solution. From the values listed in Table 2 for $\Delta \log K_M$, it is evident that for all the metal ions except Ni(II) the ternary complexes of phenoxyacetic acids and benzolin are more stable than their binary complexes. For Ni(II), low positive, zero or low negative values of $\Delta \log K_M$ have been obtained. High negative values of $\Delta \log K_M$ for salicylanilide may be due to steric hindrance caused by the bulky and freely hanging benzene nucleus in this molecule.

A comparison of $\Delta \log K_M$ values reveals, in general, the greater formation tendency of ternary 1 : 1 : 1, MAL⁺, than binary 1 : 2, ML₂, complexes. A difference in the concentrations of CuAL⁺ and CuL⁺ is consistent with the observed positive $\Delta \log K$ values in ternary complexes. The following general trend in the stability constants has been

$$\log K_{MAL}^{MA} > \log K_{ML}^M > \log K_{ML}^{ML}$$

obtained with various types of secondary ligands except salicylanilide with a few exceptions (Tables 1 and 2). For a given heteroaromatic N-base and secondary ligand, a plot of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\log K_{ML}^M$ for phenoxyacetic acids is linear (Fig. 1) which shows that the affinity of association of L with MA²⁺ in ternary systems follows, in general, the same pattern as it does with aqueous metal ion, M(H₂O)_n²⁺.

The higher stability constants of ternary complexes of Cu(II) than those of other metal ions have been explained as being due to its good π -donor properties. It is evident from Table 3 that electronegativity (SR) of phenoxyacetate anions increases but the partial negative charge (q) on coordinating O atoms decreases according to the sequence PAA > 2-CPA > 2,4-D (or 2,5-D) > 2,4,5-T (q-values). The electronegativities of 1 : 1 MA²⁺ species and partial charge on Co(II) and Ni(II) in them could not be calculated due to unavailability of SR values.

The higher formation tendency of ternary complexes of Cu(II) (produced through CuA²⁺) than the corresponding other species is obvious from these values. For example, the calculated values of electronegativities of Cu(II) and Zn(II) ions are 5.67 and 9.85, respectively, and the difference in the electronegativities of Cu(II) and CuA²⁺ species is always less than that of Zn(II) and ZnA²⁺ species.

This indicates that the SR of Cu(II) is not so diminished with a primary ligand as in the case of Zn(II). The SR of Cu(II) and Zn(II) decreases from 5.67 to 4.056 (or by 1.614) and 9.85 to 4.086 (or by 5.765) in forming Cu(bipy)²⁺ and Zn(bipy)²⁺ species, respectively. Thus, better π -donor properties of Cu(II) in CuA²⁺ than those of Zn(II) in ZnA²⁺ species have been interpreted to be due to the comparable electronegativities of CuA²⁺ and Cu(II). This also manifests M(d_π) → N(p_π) interactions⁸ in addition to σ -bonding in these complexes.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log K_{ML}^M$ vs $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ for PAA ; 2-CPA ; 2,4-D ; 2,5-D and 2,4,5-T for Cu(II) complexes (A : bipyridyl, B : phenanthroline).

Intramolecular aromatic ring stacking :

The possibility of indirect or direct ligand-ligand interactions⁹ has also been considered. These ligand-ligand interactions have been termed as intramolecular aromatic ring stacking as observed earlier¹. Phenoxyacetic acid and its chloroderivatives possess such structural characteristic that they may form open or stacked ternary complexes (Fig. 2) involving

Fig. 2. Possible structures of ternary MAL⁺ complexes [Phen-M(II)-PAA].

either one acid and another phenoxy oxygen atom (Fig. 2a) or both the oxygen atoms of carboxyl group (Fig. 2b). It is quite obvious that intramolecular aromatic ring stacking is possible only in the latter case (Fig. 2c) because in this case the side chain containing phenyl ring remains long enough to reach the ring system of N-base. This intramolecular aromatic ring stacking has been characterised by calculating the values of $\Delta \Delta \log K_M$ using the following relations.

$$\Delta \Delta \log K_M = \Delta \log K_{M(A)(2,4-D)}^M - \Delta \log K_{M(A)(PAA)}^M \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\Delta \Delta \log K_M = \Delta \log K_{M(A)(2,4,5-T)}^M - \Delta \log K_{M(A)(PAA)}^M \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta \Delta \log K_M = \Delta \log K_{M(A)(2,4,5-T)}^M - \Delta \log K_{M(A)(2,4-D)}^M \quad \dots (4)$$

Similar equations may be written by replacing PAA by 2-CPA or 2,5-D. The representative values of $\Delta \Delta \log K_M$ for Cu(II) and Zn(II) systems have been listed in Table 4. The values of Cu(II) systems are low positive, zero or low negative, but those for Zn(II) systems are always positive. This may probably be due to the different geometries of coordination sphere of the two systems. In Zn(II) complexes, the possibility of occupying an axial and an equatorial position in an octahedral coordination sphere is more than in Cu(II) complexes which prefer to occupy four equatorial positions. Hence, in Zn(II) systems intramolecular aromatic ring stacking is more favourable than in Cu(II) systems. This fact finds further support from the recent work of Sigel *et al*⁹ on the ternary complexes of aliphatic amino acids. The values of $\Delta \Delta \log K_M$ are small. Still, from their indistinguishable nature, it is evident that there should be some structural modifications as a result of direct ligand-ligand interactions. These modifications may result from intramolecular aromatic ring stacking which has a predominant role over the basicity of secondary ligands. It is possible because the size of the molecule is increasing with the increase in electronic environment around the phenyl ring due to the multiple substitution of chloro groups. Thus, the high stability of ternary complexes involving PAA is due to its high basicity

but low stacking, while those of 2-CPA, 2,5-D, 2,4-D or 2,4,5-T is due to their low basicity but high intramolecular aromatic ring stacking. The resultant effect in each case remains almost the same giving almost indistinguishable values of stability constants of ternary complexes. However, the possibility of intramolecular aromatic ring stacking could not be ruled out in the ternary complexes of banazolol or salicylanilide.

Structure-stability-activity correlations :

In order to provide quantitative information on the effect of substituent on the reactivity of side chain, the stability constants of the binary and ternary complexes of 2-CPA, 2,4-D, 2,5-D and 2,4,5-T have been correlated with Hammett substituent constants¹⁰ (σ). It has been assumed that the reaction constant, ρ , of a series of substituted 2-CPA is independent of 2-chloro group and 2-CPA itself has been given a σ value of zero. Accordingly, the σ values of 2,4-D, 2,5-D and 2,4,5-T have been used which are 0.23, 0.37 and 0.60, respectively. It has been assumed here that the 2-chloro group is absent as in the case of 4- and 5-substituted 2-methylbenzoic acids as considered by Roberts and Yancey¹¹. Least square method¹⁰ has been used to correlate pK_a , $\log K_{ML}^M$, $\log \beta_{ML_2}^M$ or $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ with σ values. The regression line (not shown) of linear correlation between pK_a and σ values has been calculated with a correlation coefficient (γ) of 0.99. Similar regression lines for $\log K_{ML}^M$ ($\log \beta_{ML_2}^M$) of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) have also been found with correlation coefficients of 0.98 (0.99), 0.93 (0.73), 0.81 (0.97) and 0.94 (0.90), respectively.

The effect of substituent on the stability constants of ternary complexes has also been examined and the representative regression lines of linear correlations have been shown in Fig. 3. It is evident from these observations that Hammett equation is equally applicable to the reactivity of 2-CPA, 2,5-D, 2,4-D and 2,4,5-T with essentially the same degree of accuracy as for 2-unsubstituted phenoxyacetic acids. These results find further support from the works of Roberts and Yancey¹¹ and El-Hilaly *et al*¹² on 4- and 5-substituted 2-methylbenzoic acids and substituted 4-pyrazolone dyes, respectively.

From above results, it appears that the formation of ternary metal complexes may create distinct

TABLE 4—PREDICTION OF AN INTRAMOLECULAR AROMATIC RING STACKING IN TERNARY COMPLEXES OF PHENOXYACETIC ACIDS

System	$\Delta \Delta \log K_M$	System	$\Delta \Delta \log K_M$
Cu(bipy)(2,4-D/PAA)	-0.02	Zn(bipy)(2,4-D/PAA)	0.02
Cu(bipy)(2,4,5-T/PAA)	-0.03	Zn(bipy)(2,4,5-T/PAA)	0.07
Cu(bipy)(2,4,5-T/2,4-D)	-0.01	Zn(bipy)(2,4,5-T/2,4-D)	0.05
Cu(phen)(2,4-D/PAA)	0.00	Zn(phen)(2,4-D/PAA)	0.03
Cu(phen)(2,4,5-T/PAA)	-0.01	Zn(phen)(2,4,5-T/PAA)	0.07
Cu(phen)(2,4,5-T/2,4-D)	-0.01	Zn(phen)(2,4,5-T/2,4-D)	0.04

Fig. 3. Least squares plots of $\log K_{MAL}^{CuA}$ vs σ for Cu(II) complexes ;

A : bipyridyl ($\log K_{MAL}^{CuA} = 3.570 - 0.151\sigma$, $r = 0.98$),

B : phenanthroline ($\log K_{MAL}^{CuA} = 3.715 - 0.168\sigma$, $r = 0.87$).

structures due to π -bonding, intramolecular aromatic ring stacking and chlorosubstitution in the phenyl ring which may be the cause of selectivity observed in the compounds of biological interest. Further, the linear correlations of stability constants of binary and ternary metal complexes of chlorophenoxyacetic acids with Hammett substituent constants,

σ , suggest that they share a common mode of action.

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